

Relative Effectiveness of Self-Instruction and Cognitive Restructuring Techniques on Attitude to Lying Among Secondary School Students in Anambra State

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Abstract

This study investigated the relative effectiveness of self-instruction and cognitive restructuring techniques on attitude to lying among secondary school students in Anambra state. One research question and one null hypothesis guided the study. Pre test, post test control quasi-experimental design was adopted. The population was 429 students who were identified by counsellors and class teachers to have positive attitude to lying in the 18 secondary schools in Awka South local Government Area, Anambra state. Three co-educational secondary schools that had the highest number of liars were selected for the study. Purposive Sampling was used to select 96 students who scored above the norm of 75 in the instrument. Thirty-item researcher developed questionnaire, Lying Attitude Inventory structured on a five-point scale ranging from 'Strongly Agree' to 'Strongly Disagree' was used for data collection. Mean and ANCOVA were used to answer the research question and test the hypothesis. Finding of the study showed that self-instruction was significantly more effective than cognitive restructuring on the students' attitude to lying. It was recommended that despite the difference in their effectiveness. Both techniques should be adopted by counsellors, teachers and significant others in secondary schools, in controlling attitude to lying among students. This is because both techniques are effective on the students' attitude to lying.

Key words: Self-instruction, Cognitive restructuring, Attitude to lying, Secondary school, Students

Introduction

Most often, children lie in situations, circumstances or events, even when it is more convenient, necessary and important to tell the truth. This may have resulted from the fact that lying is seemly, generally acceptable by individuals, and has become a norm in the society (Abodike & Unachukwu, 2020). Hence, attitude towards lying among children has become positive, because these children express favour towards lying.

Lying is common among secondary school children who use it in bid to distort real situations. According to Abodike and Ebenebe (2016), school children consistently lie and falsify real situations, without encouragement. Thus, lying is a speech act of insincere assertion wherein

the liar misrepresents truth in order to deceive. Lying therefore is a behaviour which aims at misleading and misguiding.

Some adults in the homes, schools, offices, political terrain and the society at large lie about things events and situations as such, they model lies for children. In the school, some teachers send children on errands during classes, and when these children are caught as perambulators, on reporting to the teacher, the teacher will lie that it is an important official errand. In the political terrain, all manner of lies are presented by contestants in a bid to be allowed to contest. Sometimes, they achieve victory which is celebrated in grand style. Children imbibe these values and it become part of their lives.

Lying originated from the devil who is known as the 'father of lies'(John 8:44). It is among the vices instituted and practiced by many people in the society as normal. This has lead to disorientation of many individuals' mind. However, the liar may sooner or later reap the consequences of the act. The case of Ananias and Sapphira in the scripture typifies the possible consequence of lies (Acts5; 1-10). Lying is a behavioural problem. However, it is sometimes a flexible way with good purpose of avoiding an aggressive atmosphere, but it results in creation of bad habit of regular lying, this effect among others indicate the need to control lying among children.

The causes of undesirable behaviour among students could be rooted in educational, political, social, economic, religious, health and psychological factors (Odoemelam in Abodike & Ebenebe, 2016). Abodike and Ebenebe (2016) noted that in the school, teachers who are habitual late comers lie to exonerate themselves from punishment. Students on their own part also lie to escape punishment. These lead to dishonesty in the school system.

Certain measures have been used to control undesirable behaviours among children. Dada and Okunade (2014) suggested the use of extinction and reinforcement to control undesirable behaviours. However, some teachers use punitive measures while some ignore them to fate labelling them liars.

Self-instruction is a cognitive-behavioural approach to self-control in which children are taught to use covert speech to modify their own behaviour. Children can be taught and they could learn and use a positive statement to control their own behaviour. When students are able to manage attitude to lying in their lives, they work towards being honest using their own personal efforts, and unsupervised. In the context of this study therefore, the researcher wishes to describe self-instruction as the process of involving an individual or groups of individuals in the use of a specific positive statement that can eliminate a specific undesirable behaviour to control, and gradually eliminate the positive attitude to lying, and replace it with a negative one.

The procedure for the self-instruction for this study is as follows:

- i. Model and verbalise necessary steps to complete the task
- ii. Ask the students to complete the task while the therapist verbalizes the steps
- iii. Ask the students to verbalize the steps and complete the task.
- iv. Ask the students to whisper the steps and complete the task.
- v. Ask the students to use the steps as silent talk and complete the task (Kamphaus, Reynolds & Vannest, 2008).

Cognitive restructuring is a cognitive behaviour therapy that aims at modifying distorted thinking patterns. It is the changing of irrational subconscious thought and belief to a rational conscious one. It can be used to change the belief that lying is acceptable and clever way of escaping punishment and achieving one's desires in life. In the context of this study, the researcher wishes to describe cognitive restructuring as the changing of an irrational thought and belief, which is responsible for a positive attitude to lying to a rational thought and belief that will result in a negative attitude to lying. With cognitive restructuring this wrong belief can be changed in three step procedure:

- i. leading the individual to gain awareness of detrimental thought habit
- ii. learning to challenge them
- iii. replacing them with healthy thoughts and beliefs (Abodike & Ebenebe, 2016)

Researchers like and Nwankwo and Obi (2014) and Adeusi (2013) have proved the effectiveness of self-instruction and cognitive restructuring techniques in managing different types of undesirable behaviours among students. Guidance counsellors further proved the effectiveness of self-instruction and cognitive restructuring in creating conditions that promote desirable behaviours such as clear behaviour expectations, teaching of expected behaviours and commitment (Katie & Nelson, 2012).

Generally, effectiveness is the extent to which objectives are met, that is, doing the right thing.

Attitude is an expression of favour or disfavour towards a person, a place, a thing or an event. Attitude has two dimensions, thus; positive attitude and negative attitude. Positive attitude to lying is being optimistic about lying, and denying reality. On the other hand, negative attitude to lying is to judge lying wrong (Hurka, 2014), and thereby accepting reality.

It is worth noting that previous studies on lying focused on the behaviour, and also, that the benefits associated with self-instruction and cognitive restructuring are suggestive of their credibility in the control of attitude to lying. Having observed children, some of them with positive attitude to lying, the researcher being a mentor and counsellor desired to inculcate into children, the positive statement that can reverse their attitude to lying, and compare it with the ability of children to learn, challenge and change the apparent thought and belief that lying is acceptable and clever way of escaping punishment and achieving desires. Based on this, the present study focuses on the relative effectiveness of self-instruction and cognitive restructuring techniques on attitude to lying among secondary school students in Anambra state.

Lying has several negative consequences that result in unwholesome personality development, attempts by school teachers, parents and guardians to stop lying among children using admonitions and punitive measures, have proved abortive because they have been found to be ineffective. Also, previous studies focused on lying as an act. Also studies on attitude to lying employed either self-instruction or cognitive restructuring in modifying attitude to lying. This study is concerned with comparism of effectiveness of the two techniques on the students' attitude to lying. So put in question form, the problem of this study is - what is the relative effectiveness of self-instruction and cognitive restructuring techniques on students' attitude to lying in Anambra State with the following research question and null hypothesis:

- What is the relative effectiveness of self-instruction and cognitive restructuring techniques on attitude to lying of secondary school students using their pretest and post test scores?
- There is no significant difference in the effectiveness of self-instruction and cognitive restructuring techniques on secondary school students' attitude to lying using their mean scores.

METHOD

The design for this study was the pre test post test control quasi experimental. The specific quasi design comprised the pre-test post test control group, with two experimental groups receiving treatment using self-instruction and cognitive restructuring, and a control group receiving conventional counselling. The population was 429 students. Purposive sampling was used to select 96 students from three coeducational schools that had the highest number of students with positive attitude to lying. There were 32 students in the experimental groups and the control group. The instrument for data collection was Lying Attitude Inventory (LAI), developed by the researcher. The instrument has 2 parts, A and B. Part A solicited information on the bio-data of the students. Part B contained 30 items that has fifteen positive and fifteen negative statements. The participants were required to indicate their level of agreement with each statement choosing from a four-point scale of Strongly Agree, (SA, 4 points), Agree, (A, 3 points), Disagree, (D, 2 points), and Strongly Disagree, (SD, 1 point).

For the first fifteen items, the highest score was sixty (positive attitude) while the lowest was fifteen (negative attitude), and for the last fifteen items the highest score was sixty (negative attitude) while the lowest was fifteen (positive attitude). To get the total score for each subject, the values in the direct score items and those in the reversed score items were added up.

The face and content validity of the instrument were established by three experts, two in the Department of Guidance and Counselling and one in Measurement and Evaluation, all from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. A trial test was done using 20 participants. The scores obtained were used to establish the reliability measure of the instrument. Split half was done and using Cronbach Alpha statistics, a reliability coefficient of $r=0.92$ was obtained. This was considered adequate for the study.

The self-instruction procedure used involved the following steps:

- i) Model and verbalise necessary steps to complete the task. Here, the therapist verbalised the self talk, 'I must avoid lying in order to live positively, function well, and grow into a wholesome person'.
- ii) Ask the students to complete the task while the therapist verbalizes the steps. Here, the students gradually developed the urge to eliminate favour towards lying, as they attentively focused on the therapist, while she strongly, strictly and emphatically verbalized the positive statement.
- iii) Ask the students to verbalize the steps and complete the task. Here, the students were asked to verbalize the positive statement with full attention, concentration and focus.
- iv) Ask the students to whisper the steps and complete the task. In this step, the students were asked to whisper the positive statement with attention, concentration and focus.

v) Ask the students to use the steps as silent talk and complete the task. Here, the students were asked to internally say the positive statement to themselves, in the face of any situation that trigger them to lie.

The cognitive restructuring method used in this study is patterned after Abodike and Ebenebe (2016) therapeutic method, which has the following procedure thus;

The cognitive restructuring method used for the experimental group was as follows:

1. Sensitisation and awareness creation on the detrimental consequences of lying.

Incorporation of new facts (cognitive contents) to redesign the cognitive structure thus;

-Lying is being false, dishonest, deceptive, immoral and evil

-Lying is living negatively and this separates one from reality

Lying leads to destruction of trust from others, and loss of integrity.

Lying causes stress, tension and anxiety

Lying causes inconsistency and instability in daily living

-Lying distorts wholesome personality development-

-Lying destroys life and results in untimely death.

2. Challenging the thought and belief that 'lying is an easy way to escape punishment and achieve desires in life'.

Cognitive challenge and refutation, thus;

-Can I reject this thought?

Ans: Yes I can

-Can I accept this thought?

Ans: Yes I can

-Can I support this thought?

Ans: No I cannot

-What evidence exists for the falseness of this thought and belief?

Ans: The incidences of Ananias and Sapphira, two judges who lied against Susanna and a harlot that claimed the living baby before King Solomon. All these evidences are in the holy Bible.

-Does any evidence exist for the truthfulness of this thought and belief?

Ans: No, however, one may achieve one's desires, immediately, by lying. Nevertheless such achievements carry with them tension and anxiety, and they neither last nor stand the test of time

-What worst thing could actually happen to me if I fail to get what I think I must get immediately?

Ans: Nothing at all, but disappointment which is very normal in life. However, with hard work, perseverance, commitment and dedication, one can get whatever one desires in life, by honest means.

3. Replacement with the thought and belief that 'one can escape punishment and achieve desires in life by telling the truth'.

Introduction of facts into the cognitive structure, thus;

-Truth is life and once there is life, there is hope.

-Hope founded on truth could lead to attainment of life desires.

-The incidences of a prostitute who actually owned the living baby, the thief on the cross and the beautiful Susanna, lied against by two judges, all in the holy Bible among others are evidences that one can achieve one's desires by telling the truth.

-The harlot who owned the living baby, the thief on the cross, and the beautiful Susanna achieved their desires by telling the truth.

-Similar experiences occurred and will continue to occur in life, where truth had prevailed and will continue to prevail. This is because truth is authority and authority is never the truth.

-Therefore, one can escape punishment and achieve desires by telling the truth and being true.

The control group was given conventional counselling on the origin, meaning and consequences of lying.

Data collected was analysed using means to answer the research question and ANCOVA to test the hypothesis.

Table 1: Pretest and Posttest on the Relative Effectiveness of Self-instruction and Cognitive Restructuring Techniques on Attitude to Lying of Secondary School Students (Norm = 75.00)

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
Self-instruction	32	77.25	22.19	55.05	More Effective
Cognitive Restru.Tech.	32	77.44	31.59	45.85	

In table 1, it was observed that the students treated with self-instruction technique had pretest mean score of 77.25 and posttest mean score of 22.19 with lost mean 55.05 in their attitude to lying, while those in the cognitive restructuring technique had pretest mean score of 77.44 and posttest mean score of 31.59 with lost mean 45.85 in their attitude to lying. The post test mean scores of the two groups were reduced below the base line which is 75. However, the mean loss for self-instruction is greater than the mean loss for cognitive restructuring. This showed that self-instruction technique is more effective than cognitive restructuring in reducing the students' attitude to lying in Anambra state.

Table 2: ANCOVA on the Posttest Attitude to Lying Mean Scores of Students Treated with Self-instruction Technique and those Treated with Cognitive restructuring technique

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	1458.594	2	729.297			
Intercept	0.314	1	0.314			
PRETEST	42.954	1	42.954			
METHOD	1412.580	1	1412.580	64.03	0.000	S
Error	1345.640	61	22.060			
Total	49083.000	64				
Corrected Total	2804.234	63				

Table 2 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 61df denominator, the calculated F is 64.03 with Pvalue of 0.00 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the third null hypothesis is rejected. So, there is significant difference in the effectiveness of self-instruction and cognitive restructuring techniques on secondary school students' attitude to lying.

Discussion

From the analysis of the result in respect to research question 3, self-instruction and cognitive restructuring techniques were effective on attitude to lying among the students. This is evident in their mean scores on Lying Attitude Inventory. This is in line with Nkebem and Okon (2006) and Nwankwo and Obi (2014) which proved the effectiveness of self-instruction in managing undesirable behaviours among students.

Cognitive restructuring, also proved effective on the students' attitude to lying. This finding is in line with that of Gross, Hamilton, Harrison, Phelps and Roy (2012) which compared treatment of conditioned emotional disorder with cognitive restructuring and control, and suggested that cognitive restructuring has durable effects on behavioural problem. Shurick (2012) also supported the finding that cognitive restructuring group demonstrated a significant reduction in mean differential across sessions, whereas this effect was not seen in the control group. Shurick further demonstrated that when subjects were given a specific contextual frame, they will apply it when subsequently presented with the same image even without being cued. The finding is suggestive that individuals with learned undesirable behaviour can be trained to use individually generated reappraisals to change the meaning associated with the behaviour inducing stimulus. Hence, the effectiveness of cognitive restructuring on attitude to lying.

Hypothesis showed that there was a significant difference in the post test mean scores of self-instruction and cognitive restructuring in their mean scores on Lying Attitude Inventory. Nevertheless, the two techniques were quite effective. However, more effectiveness on attitude to lying by self-instruction could be as a result of the simplicity and ease in its application.

Conclusion

The study revealed that self-instruction was more effective than cognitive restructuring on the student's attitude to lying. It also showed that experimental and control groups differ significantly in their mean scores for self-instruction and cognitive restructuring techniques.

Recommendations

Despite the fact that self-instruction was more effective than cognitive restructuring insignificantly, guidance counsellors in secondary schools should adopt both techniques in controlling attitude to lying among students because they are effective techniques, and therefore, useful. This will help them to manage this behavioural challenge of positive attitude to lying among students.

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